

Psychological Flexibility and its Relationship to Professional Adaptation among Teachers of Students with Special Needs in Jordan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 13,2023</p> <p>Accepted: October 14,2023</p> <p>Keywords : Psychological Stress, Professional Compatibility</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10003471</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between psychological stress and professional adjustment among special education teachers, and to investigate the differences between males and females on the psychological stress scale as well as on the professional adjustment scale, and to investigate the differences between the sample members who have experience with individuals who do not have experience (experience over five years), on the psychological stress scale as well as on the professional compatibility scale. The study sample consisted of male and female special education teachers in the capital, Amman, and their number was (344) teachers (185) female teachers, (159) male teachers. The sample will be drawn according to Richard Geiger's law for accurate sampling (0.05) The researcher will use the psychological stress scale, and the professional compatibility scale (prepared by the researcher).</i></p>

Introduction

The teaching profession is a demanding and multi-variable profession, as the role of the professor is almost limited to the mere preparation and implementation of the teaching process, but also to the necessity of following up on various scientific and technological developments and familiarity with the latest educational methods and methods, as well as making decisions to contribute to solving academic and educational problems in addition to the need to open up to society and work on his service, and all this is done in light of the society's low view of this profession and the absence of support and encouragement. The teacher does not have authority and prestige, whether inside or outside the school, and at the same time he is asked for many tasks imposed on him through legislation and educational instructions (Akoun, 2012). The teaching profession is a hard and tiring profession that may make teachers suffer a lot from many difficulties and obstacles that may generate several pressures in the field of professional life, so that these pressures result from many reasons, which may be due to the life that the professor lives or to the circumstances surrounding him in all aspects (economic, social, cultural, family, academic, etc). All of these factors and influences lead the student to distress, frustration, despair and failure in the exercise of his scholastic activity and possibly affect his level of professional performance, and his psychological and physical health. This will cause an increase in his psychological stress level. Since the professor is the foundation on which the educational process is based, he must enjoy good mental and physical health and an integrated and balanced personality that reflects an acceptable level of satisfaction with the professional and practical life that the professor lives, as his outlook on life is directly reflected on his students (Khalu, 2019)

Life is full of several pressures that afflict man, because he lives in an era full of conflicts, contradictions and problems, and the demands of life increase, resulting in severe stressful situations and sources of anxiety, tension and threat factors. As individuals at all stages of their lives may be exposed to severe situations and influences from many sources such as home, work and society, especially the profession of education. This may be due to the complexity of lifestyles. (Arees, 2017).

1.2 The Study Problem

The phenomenon of psychological stress affects all professions, and this depends on the importance of the relationship with the other, but some professions remain more sensitive than others in terms of the person's interaction with others, such as the profession of education. In this profession, the friction with the other is strong, and this friction may lead to a person's depletion of his energies. The results of some studies have found a positive and high correlation between work pressures that teachers are exposed to during the exercise of their profession and the areas of emotional exhaustion and dull feelings, and a negative relationship in the field of lack of achievement, On the other hand, the compatibility of the teacher with his profession is necessary in order for him to be able to carry out his duty to the fullest. The professionally compatible teacher is linked to his profession on the basis of satisfaction with the income he brings in economic or social status. Many studies have

indicated the positive relationship between professional compatibility and the teacher's practice of his professional life to the fullest.

Hence, this study comes to address psychological stress and its relationship to professional adjustment among a sample of male and female teachers of the special education stage in the capital, Amman, in the light of the variables of gender and experience.

1.3 The Study Questions

The study questions are determined by the following:

1. What is the relationship between psychological stress and professional adjustment among a sample of special education teachers in the capital, Amman?
2. Are there statistically significant differences between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the gender variable?
3. Are there statistically significant differences between the average responses of the sample members on the professional compatibility scale according to the gender variable?
4. Are there statistically significant differences between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the experience variable?
5. Are there statistically significant differences between the average responses of the sample members on the professional compatibility scale according to the experience variable?

1.4 Research Importance

The importance of the study, both theoretical and practical, is as follows:

1. Study of the relationship between psychological stress and professional adjustment among a sample of special education teachers in the capital, Amman.
2. The practical importance appears in the results it produces through which officials, decision-makers and administration can be directed to alleviating the psychological pressures of special education teachers.

1.5 Research Aims

This study aims to:

1. Determining the nature of the relationship between psychological stress and professional adjustment among a sample of male and female teachers of special education in the capital, Amman.
2. Investigating the differences between the average responses of the sample members on the two scales of psychological stress and occupational adjustment according to the gender variable.
3. Know the differences between the average responses of the sample members on the scales of psychological stress and occupational adjustment according to the variable of experience.

1.6 Definition of Terms

Psychological stress

It is the psychological state that affects the primary education professor in the teaching profession in terms of personal, health, and family, and this may be due to his inability to face the difficulties and obstacles he faces in his professional life. This is expressed by the number of scores obtained by each member of the sample on this scale.

Professional compatibility

It is the ability of the primary education teacher to adapt and adapt with the school to achieve satisfaction in the teaching profession. This is expressed by the number of scores obtained by each member of the sample on this scale.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The issue of stress has received great attention from scholars and researchers, due to the fact that a person is exposed to several problems, obstacles and difficulties in his life. Where does it affect him from several aspects, including psychological and professional. As for the field of teaching, we find that these pressures may differ and vary from one professor to another, in terms of their intensity and intensity, when they are required to confront and challenge them to achieve an appropriate compatibility and adaptation in the professional field.

Sources of psychological stress

When looking at the relationship that binds the individual to his society, it seems to us that these pressures result from different several Psychological sources and are represented by external sources and internal sources:

External sources of psychological stress

- Family pressures: family conflicts, divorce, separation, frequent arguments, children.

- Occupational pressures: disagreements with colleagues, many legislations and laws, job dissatisfaction, low wages, conflict within the institution ... etc.
- Financial or economic pressures: such as low incomes, high unemployment rates, and high crime rates.
- Social pressures: In turn, according to the multiplicity of social relationships themselves, they are divided into social relationships. The individual, if he is married or unmarried, the number of actions if he is married, as well as the public and private environmental and family situation that lives in the shadow of the individual. These variables are within the social factor, as they leave certain reactions in the form of psychological pressures on the individual, even if their sources are different and their impact varies. Social pressures include isolation, parties, experiences of physical and sexual abuse, neglect of children, and behavioral abnormalities.

Internal sources of psychological stress

- Emotional pressures: Emotion in man is an instinct that God has reserved for humans without the rest of the creatures, as it represents human beings and is one of the requirements of his human existence, when a person is hindered in seeking marriage and family stability for some reason, his psychological life is forced.
Emotional life makes a person stable and balanced, and any influence on this aspect weakens the individual's resistance to stressful life events.
- Internal psychological events and problems: Emotion in reasonable degrees, protects man from danger, mobilizes his energies for work and activity and pushes him to resist dangers, and enemies to face the future, but in some cases, emotions may turn into a source of disturbance in psychological and social life because of its physical functions and what is related to advice or disease (Daily, 2013).

2.2 Previous Studies

Asikainen&Katajavuori (2023) study aimed to investigate whether or whether students with varying degrees of psychological flexibility have had notably different experiences with burnout and online studying during COVID-19. N = 296 first-year students majoring in life sciences provided the data, which was gathered in the spring of 2021. Pearson's correlation and linear regression were used to examine the association between mental adaptability and academic exhaustion. Inductive content analysis was used to categorise and quantify students' free-text comments about their experiences with online education. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's test were used to determine differences in study-related burnout, and a Chi-square test was used to determine variations in online learning experiences across the three groups of respondents (high, medium, and poor psychological flexibility). The data demonstrated an inverse association between openness to new experiences and academic fatigue. There were also statistically significant differences in how each group dealt with academic fatigue and how they used the internet to do their coursework.

Biglan et al. (2023) stated that early childhood special educators often experience significant levels of stress and burnout, which has been linked to high rates of turnover, lower educational effectiveness, and greater staff turnover. In both its preventative and therapeutic applications, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) shows great promise. This pilot study tested the efficacy of ACT workshops on teachers' stress-related problems (i.e., stress, depression, and burnout) and on teachers' ability to assist one another in the classroom for children with developmental impairments. Reports of despair, stress, and burnout were significantly related to EA and MA scores taken before the study began. Staff members' EA dropped, while teachers' MA and VL rose, and their confidence in their own abilities was boosted by the intervention. This data demonstrates that ACT workshops can have a positive effect on parameters related to burnout, stress, and depression in the field of special education for young children.

Salah et al. (2022) study used a convenience sample of 487 Jordanian elementary school students to examine the predictability of optimism and its relationship with psychological flexibility among a population that has been exposed to significant psychological and sociological stressors since the outbreak of COVID-19, which has had a profound impact on the development of students' identities, networks of support, understanding of self and others, motivation for learning, and overall academic performance. The information was analysed using a descriptive method. Student optimism and psychological flexibility were found to be modest, with a positive, statistically significant association in favour of females. Because of the positive correlation between optimism prediction ability and psychological flexibility among students, the study advises parents, educators, social workers, and policymakers to work towards improving these traits before, during, and after the COVID-19 Pandemic. To fully grasp how the Coronavirus pandemic affected the students' levels of optimism and psychological flexibility, as well as their sociological psychology, it was suggested that future researchers employ a variety of qualitative methods, such as observation and interviews, to gather rich and authentic data about the students' real behaviours and perspectives.

Al-Khairy(2013) study entitled: Emotional intelligence and its relationship to psychological stress, a sample of working mothers in light of some demographic and family variables in Muhail Governorate Asir, the research aims to identify the level of both emotional intelligence and psychological stress of working mothers in the province of Asir. The emotional prepared by Othman and Rizk, the modified version of Al-Balawi (2004), and the abbreviation of the Sabban scale (2003), and the researcher used the following statistical methods: the averages, the standard deviation, the Pearson correlation coefficient, and the analysis of unilateral variance. Low among working mothers in MuhaylAsir governorate, and there is a negative correlation statistically significant between emotional intelligence scores and psychological stress levels among working mothers in Muhayl governorate.

Kateh(2016) conducted a study entitled: Psychological stress and its relationship to the rise of the value system among kindergarten teachers, a field study in the city of Baghdad. The aim of the research is to study psychological stress and its relationship to the rise of the value system among kindergarten teachers and showed that kindergarten teachers use various methods related to their psychological characteristics and the nature of the events themselves to confront some stressful events, some of them can deal with the event flexibly and bear the pressure and adapt to it and improve their performance and some of them deal With him in a rigid and negative manner and feels like a threat to her and a danger to her. This exacerbates their feelings of psychological pressure, and they are based on their background about the personal meanings and special indications that teachers add to their methods of dealing with stressful events. The study aimed to identify the psychological pressures of kindergarten teachers and their relationship to the rise of their values. To achieve the aim of the study, the researcher used the descriptive approach. The sample of the study was (150 female teachers) who were randomly selected from the study population of government kindergarten teachers in the city of Baghdad / Rusafa side. The researcher used two scales of psychological stress (prepared by the researcher), and adopted the scale of the rise of the value system from (Shamekh and Al-Hamdani, 2010), and the study reached several results, including that the higher the value system of the kindergarten teacher, the less psychological pressure she has Recommendations and suggestions.

Al-Amiri (2016) conducted a study entitled: Psychological Stress of the Displaced. The aim of the research is to identify the psychological stress of the displaced, the researcher used a psychological stress scale from his numbers, the research was applied to a sample of the displaced in the city of Baghdad, and the research reached the following results: The high level of psychological stress among the displaced in general, and the results showed that the arithmetic mean of the field Psychological stress came in the first place with a value of (42.993), and in the second place came the health field with a value of (37.026), and in the third place came the economic field with a value of (34.306), and in the fourth place came the security field with a value of (24.793), and in the fifth place came the field With regard to identifying the significance of the difference in psychological stress according to the gender variable among displaced males and females, it was found that there are differences between males and females in the psychological stress scale in favor of females, and a set of recommendations were presented to the relevant authorities.

Mustafa (2015) conducted a study entitled: Psychological stress among female teachers in autism centers in Khartoum locality and its relationship to some variables. The study aimed to know the level of psychological stress among teachers of autistic children in autism centers in Khartoum locality. The researcher adopted the descriptive analytical approach. To collect the data, the psychological stress scale for teachers was used (Medhat Mansour and Viola Al-Bilawi 1989 AD). The total research community reached 46 teachers. Of them, 40 female teachers participated as a sample for the study, they were tested by the intentional method of processing information, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used, and the research reached the following results: The psychological pressures of teachers of autistic children in special education centers in Khartoum locality are characterized by high. There are statistically significant differences in the psychological stress of teachers of autistic children, according to the age variable in favor of the age group 20-29. There are statistically significant differences in the psychological stress of teachers of autistic children, according to the educational qualification variable, in favor of the university educational level. There are statistically significant differences in the psychological stress of teachers of autistic children, according to the profession variable in favor of the profession of psychological researcher. The research also included a number of recommendations and variables.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

The study approach is the descriptive approach that shows the correlation between the variables, and it is the most appropriate approach to the nature of this study, as it provides a description of the studied phenomenon without changing its nature, as well as allowing the study to be applied to a wider sample.

3.2 The study population and its sample

The study population consists of all male and female teachers in the special education stage in the capital, Amman. In order to find a representative sample of the original community, the sample was drawn

according to Richard Geiger law, with an accuracy of (05.0), so that the number of sample members will be (344) male and female teachers, (185) female teachers, and (159) male teachers, the study will be conducted during the academic year (2022-2023) in the schools of the capital, Amman.

3.3 Statistical Treatment

The study will use the SPSS program for statistical analysis, and to achieve the purposes of the study.

3.4 The Study Tools

After reviewing the Arab and foreign studies related to the subject of this study, the researcher designed the psychological stress scale as well as the professional compatibility scale for teachers of the special education stage.

The psychological stress scale included basic data that included the following variables: the gender variable, and the experience variable. The scores were distributed on the scale's (20 items) by giving a degree (5) for the possibility of high stress, and degree (4) (for the possibility of a lot of stress, and degree (3) for the possibility of some pressure, grade (2) for the possibility of a little pressure, and grade (1) for the possibility of no pressure.

As for the occupational compatibility scale, it included basic data, which included the following variables: the gender variable, the experience variable. The scores were distributed on the (26) items of the scale, giving the degree (5) for the probability that I strongly agree, the degree (4) for the probability that I agree, the degree (3) for the possibility sometimes, and the degree (2) for the possibility I disagree, and the degree (1) for the possibility I strongly disagree.

Results and discussion

To answer the first study question, which states: What is the relationship between psychological stress and professional adjustment among a sample of teachers in the basic education stage in Amman/Jordan?

The following hypothesis was formulated which states:

1. The first hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between psychological stress and professional compatibility among a sample of basic education teachers in Amman/Jordan.

To test the first hypothesis, the Pearson correlation coefficient was used, and Table No. (1) shows the population and sample size according to educational regions.

Table 1: Distribution of male and female teachers in the basic education stage according to educational regions

Sample	Abdali area	Ras Al Ain area	Zahran area	Yarmouk area	Al-Hafa area	Total
Population	3427	2415	4011	1308	1016	12177
Sample	145	142	137	125	139	688

Table 2: Distribution of sample members according to gender variable

Sample	Abdali area	Ras Al Ain area	Zahran area	Yarmouk area	Al-Hafa area	Total
Males	64	70	58	54	72	318
Females	77	77	79	69	68	370

Table 3 shows the relationship between psychological stress, professional adjustment, and the associated results:

	Psychological stress	Significance level	Probability value	The decision
Professional compatibility	0.027	0.05	0.472	Not statistically significant

Table No. (3) shows that there is no statistically significant relationship between psychological stress and professional compatibility. This means that the first hypothesis has been fulfilled. The value of the correlation coefficient reached (0.027) at a significance level of (0.472). Since the probability value (sig) is (0.47) greater than (0.05), we accept the null hypothesis.

The reason for this is that the various life pressures that the teacher is exposed to do not necessarily have any relationship or connection to creating a level of compatibility in the individual that helps him in professional success on the one hand, and in understanding his personality and solving his problems on the other hand, every individual is able to carry out this process of self-control with regard to separating what

psychological pressures may affect the profession or any other activity, the successful teacher is the teacher who realizes the necessity of separating his personal problems on the one hand from his work on the other hand, and he is the one who can isolate external environmental influences from his level of professional compatibility.

To answer the second study question, which states: Is there a statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the gender variable? The following hypothesis was formulated:

The second hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the gender variable.

To study the differences between males and females on the psychological stress scale, according to the arithmetic mean as well as the standard deviation, as well as calculating the value of t and its level of significance, as the following table shows:

Table 4. Average responses of males and females and their standard deviation on the psychological stress scale

Gender	N	Mean	STD	T	Sig
Male	318	3.5452	.57716	1.107	.268
Female	370	3.5109	.56790		

Table No. (4) shows that the value of (t) reached (17.10) at a significance level of (0.268). This means that there are no statistically significant differences between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the gender variable, and therefore the hypothesis is fulfilled.

This result can be interpreted to mean that the life and professional pressures that male and female teachers are exposed to are the same, with no difference between them. Thus, the result shows that the person is exposed to pressure, whether male or female, the same things that can cause stress for teachers in school can cause stress for female teachers, such as dealing with the administration, dealing with parents, dealing with students, and the abundance of study materials.

To answer the third study question, which states: Is there a statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the professional compatibility scale according to the gender variable? The following hypothesis was formulated:

The third hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the professional compatibility scale according to the gender variable.

To study the differences between males and females on the professional compatibility scale, according to the arithmetic mean as well as the standard deviation, as well as calculate the value of t and its level of significance, as the following table shows:

Table 5. Average responses of males and females and their standard deviation on the professional compatibility scale

Gender	N	Mean	STD	T	Sig
Male	318	3.8166	.47478	1.336	.182
Female	370	3.7679	.47893		

Table No. (5) shows that the value of (t) is (1.33) at a significance level of (0.182), which means that the hypothesis is fulfilled.

The reason for this could be the similar psychological mechanism between both sexes, as the amount of psychosocial influence does not differ much in relation to the surrounding variables, whether on males or on females, especially in professions that do not require great effort, and the teaching profession is one of the desirable professions for both males and females.

To answer the study's four questions, which states: Is there a statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the experience variable? The following hypothesis was formulated:

Hypothesis Four: There is no statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the psychological stress scale according to the experience variable.

To study the differences between sample members who have experience and those who do not have experience on the psychological stress scale, according to the arithmetic mean as well as the standard deviation, as well as calculating the value of t and its level of significance, as the following table shows:

Table 6. Average responses of the sample according to the experience variable and their standard deviation on the psychological stress scale

Experience	N	Mean	STD	T	Sig
Less than five years	230	3.5350	.55541	.380	.704
Five years and more	458	3.5226	.58079		

Table No. (6) shows that the value of (t) is (0.38) at the significance level (0.704). This means that there are no differences and therefore the hypothesis is fulfilled.

This can be explained by the fact that teachers acquire more experience during in-service training before joining the teaching profession, so differences between teachers in terms of experience do not appear, and if differences exist, they are weak.

To answer the fifth study question, which states: Is there a statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the professional compatibility scale according to the experience variable? The following hypothesis was formulated:

Fifth hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference between the average responses of the sample members on the professional compatibility scale according to the experience variable.

To study the differences between sample members who have experience and those who do not have experience on the psychological adjustment scale, according to the arithmetic mean as well as the standard deviation, as well as calculating the value of t and its level of significance, as the following table shows:

Table 7. Average sample responses according to the experience variable and their standard deviation on the professional compatibility scale

Experience	N	Mean	STD	T	Sig
Less than five years	230	3.8132	.42688	.888	.375
Five years and more	458	3.7789	.50075		

Table No. (7) shows that the value of (t) is (0.88) at the significance level (0.375). This means that there are no statistically significant differences, and therefore the hypothesis is fulfilled.

This may be due to the greater the number of years of experience due to the period spent by the teacher or school working in the teaching profession, the greater the burdens and thus their ability to deal with them in an optimal manner increases and their ability to bear the responsibility placed on them increases. This is matched by the enthusiasm and motivation of teachers who have recently joined or spent a short period in this profession, and this may explain the fading effect of experience on teachers' sense of compatibility with the teaching profession.

Discussion of the Results

Teachers of elementary school students in Amman, Jordan, were studied to determine how stress affected their ability to do their jobs.

1. Relation Between Psychological Stress and Professional Compatibility

The first hypothesis was based on the first research question, which posited that elementary school teachers in Amman, Jordan, do not show a significant correlation between psychological stress and professional compatibility.

The sample was statistically representative of Amman's educational landscape. The Pearson correlation coefficient in Table 3 supports the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant link between psychological stress and work-related compatibility. The significance level for the correlation coefficient is rather low, at 0.472.

The results imply that a teacher's professional compatibility is unrelated to the stresses of their home life. A good educator is one who can separate their private life from their teaching without letting the latter suffer.

2. Psychological Stress According to Gender

The second enquiry concerned whether or not the results of a psychological stress scale varied with respect to gender. According to the findings, there is no discernible difference in how men and women responded. This data implies that male and female educators are subject to the same kinds of personal and professional stresses. It appears that administrative interactions, family engagement, student behaviour, and curricular demands are equally stressful for both male and female educators.

3. Professional Compatibility According to Gender

Examining whether or whether there are any disparities in how men and women rate their professional compatibility was the third research issue. No observable variation in response rates was seen between sexes

once again. It appears that regardless of the challenges they face, teachers of both sexes have comparable views about their compatibility with the profession. This could indicate that male and female educators are equally affected by external influences, or that there is a consistent psychological mechanism across genders.

4. Psychological Stress According to Experience

The fourth research question looked at how instructors' stress levels varied with their level of expertise in the field. The data shows that classroom teachers with five years of experience or fewer are just as effective as those with more expertise. This finding may imply that teachers don't need additional experience to handle the stress of their jobs because they are well prepared by their initial in-service training.

5. Professional Compatibility According to Experience

The influence of years in the workforce on personal chemistry was the topic of the fifth enquiry. There is no statistically significant difference between newer and more seasoned educators, according to the research. This finding could be viewed as evidence that more seasoned educators are better equipped to handle the unique demands of their profession. Newer instructors, however, who are typically more enthused and driven, may experience a similar sense of fit. It's possible that the lack of difference in responses based on experience is due to this equilibrium.

In conclusion, the study finds that teachers in Amman and Jordan who educate elementary school students are resilient enough to handle psychological stress without sacrificing their work relationships. Stress and compatibility assessments also show no discernible differences across gender or years of experience. These results shed light on the strength and flexibility of educators of various backgrounds and levels of experience in the face of adversity in the classroom.

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